

PARASITOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DIAGNOSIS OF INTESTINAL PARASITOSIS IN LARGE FELINES FROM BUCHAREST ZOO

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Abstract

The study was carried out on several animal species from the collection of the Bucharest Zoo in the period 2015-2020 and the evolution of parasitic infestations among others was studied. In the first phase, the rate of intestinal endoparasites was monitored in large felines, where the infestation rate was 41.6% in some cases, correlating with progressive weakening and digestive disorders. According to the results, *Toxascaris leonina* infestation was prevalent especially in tigers.

Keywords: large felines, tigers, endoparasitosis, *Toxascaris*.

Introduction

The pathology of captive animals involves a particular approach strictly conditioned by the way they are kept. Space restriction , feeding way, disclaim of territorial behaviour and the impact of the visitors are all factors that lead captive animals to develop a specific pathology (Hasslinger, 1985).

Big cats of genus *Panthera*(tiger,lion,jaguar) and *Felis*(cougar, lynx) exhibit good adaptability in zoos, the proof being found in their prolificacy(Atanaskova, Gonzales 2007). They are found in all collections in zoos in the country in a large enough number. Clinical and laboratory examinations conducted by Micu et al. indicated long periods of *Toxascaris leonina* infestations , many of them due to contamination with infested eggs in the living environment.

Materials and methods

The study was performed by laboratory and clinical examinations during march 2015- august 2020 on five species of big cats:*Pantera tigris*(tiger), *Pantera leo*(lion), *Pantera onca*(jaguar), *Felis concolor*(cougar) and *Felis lynx*(lynx) from the Bucharest Zoo collection.

24 animals werw under examination among eleven (11)Siberian tigers, four(4)jaguars, three(3)cougars, three(3) lynx, two(2)lions and one Bengal tiger, their feces were collected for coproparasitary examination. The coproparasitary examination used qualitative methods such as Willis, Andersen sucrose, Perez Fontana and quantitative such Mini-Flotac and McMaster.It aimed to identify forms of contamination (eggs, oocysts,cysts)and also adult parasites removed spontaneously or after treatment. Infected animals were subjected to antihelmintic tratement with benzimidazole derivats, praziquantel and levamisole. Comments upon reinfection possibilities and resistance of invasion forms led to the establishment of an ongoing program of periodic coprologic examinations and prophylactic treatments

Results and discussion

Out of the total number of animals,10(41,6%) were identified with intestinal parasitic infestations(tab.1)

Tab 1.

Prevalence of enteric parasitosis

Felines examined	Felines infested	%
24	10	41,6

Incidence in the species was as follows:4 siberian tigers – 40%, 2 cougars- 20%, 2 lynx-20%, 1 lion- 10% and 1 jaguar- 10%. In all these cases, infestations with *Toxascaris leonina*, *Strongyloides* sp. and *Isospora* sp. were identified(tab.2)

Tab 2.

Incidence of parasitic infestations by species

No. total of infested felines	Species infested					
	Siberian tiger	Bengal tiger	Puma	Jaguar	Lion	lynx
10	Nr. %	Nr. %	Nr. %	Nr. %	Nr. %	Nr. %
	4 40	0	2 20	1 10	1 10	2 20

Infestation with *Toxascaris leonina* was met in 5(50%)cases and its level was 500-1000 epg (eggs per gram). Infestation with *Isospora* sp.was met in 3 (30%)cases and the level was 200 epg(eggs per gram). Infestation with *Strongyloides* sp. was met in two (20%) cases and it was of 200 epg(eggs per gram).(tab.3 and 4)

Tab 3.

Incidence of *Toxascaris leonina*

Total no. felines infested	Felines infested with <i>Toxascaris leonina</i>	
	No.	%
10	5	50

Tab 4.

Incidence of *Isoospora sp.*

Total no. felines infested	Felines infested with <i>Isoospora sp.</i>	
	Nr.	%
10	3	30

Fig. 2 *Strongyloides stercoralis*-egg

Conclusions

1. The incidence infestations in big cats from the Bucharest Zoo collection was of 41,6 %
2. Infestations with *Toxocaris leonina* (50%), *Strongyloides* sp. (20%), *Isospora* sp.(20%).
3. The degree of infestation was of 500-100 epg with *Toxascaris leonina*, 200 epg with *Strongyloides* sp. and 200 epg with *Isospora* sp.
4. Curative and prophylactic treatments were based on benzimidazole derivates (fenbendazole and mebendazole), levamisole and praziquantel.

References

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